

Deliverable 2.4 – AtlantECO-MAPS1

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1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	Lead authors: Meike Vogt (ETHZ), Fabio Benedetti (ETHZ), Daniele de Angelis (UNIROMA), Luigi Maiorano (UNIROMA) Contributing authors: Dominic Eriksson (ETHZ), Nielja Knecht (ETHZ), Giacomo Poli (ETHZ), Xinhang Li (ETHZ), Olivier Jaillon (CEA/GENOSCOPE), Paul Frémont (CEA/GENOSCOPE), Fabien Lombard (SU), Lionel Guidi (SU), Erik Van Sebille (UU), Marion Gehlen (CEA), Germain Benard (CEA), Thomas Frölicher (UBern), Tim Collart (SBE)	Content contributions	04.12.2023
0.2	Meike Vogt (ETHZ)	Inclusion of changes by co-authors	12.01.2024
1.0	Eloïse Trabut (SZN)	Formatting and submission	17.01.2024

2 Executive summary

This deliverable reports on Task 2.3 ‘Map microbiomes, plastics, the plastisphere, carbon flux and derived ecosystem structure and functions’. It uses state-of-the-art species distribution models calibrated carefully to account for the spatiotemporal biases typical for marine ecosystem data to extrapolate and map some of the data sets delivered in AtlantECO-BASE1 (D2.1; Vogt et al., 2023) to the global scale. Maps included into AtlantECO-MAPS1 consisted of contributions based on data from the five following data sources and tasks: Task 2.2.1 ‘Microbiome data from traditional microscopy (presence-absence, abundance and biomass)’, Task 2.2.2 ‘Microbiome data from state-of-the-art optical/imaging analysis’, Task 2.2.3 ‘Microbiome and plastisphere data from state-of-the-art genetic analyses’, Task 2.2.4 ‘Nano-, micro and macroplastics data from state-of-the-art sampling methods’, and Task 2.2.5 ‘Carbon flux data from estimated from high resolution bio-optical sensors’. Additionally, this task also provides a list of data visualisation apps and modelling pipelines specifically developed for this project and task. Furthermore, we report on the range of maps that is now hosted on the AtlantECO GenoNode (<https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/>) as planned in Task 10.1.3 and in agreement with deliverable D10.3. A comprehensive list and description of all mapped products collected can be found in the Appendix Tables to this document.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction & Methodology

In recent years, the number of marine observations of plankton occurrence, biomass, taxonomic or functional diversity, traits and/or species distributions has increased exponentially. However, marine plankton observations remain sparse in space and time, making the interpretation of raw data prone to large uncertainties (Righetti et al., 2023). The statistical exploitation of the underlying relationships between biological target variables and environmental predictors known, or suspected, to constrain the realised environmental niche or spatiotemporal distribution of the target, commonly referred to as ‘species distribution modelling’ or ‘niche modelling’, can help alleviate issues related to data scarcity and sampling biases. Such statistical data analysis can also be used to model and extrapolate (i.e., map) observation-driven information to under-sampled ocean regions or to potential future states of the ocean and climate. To this end, models must be calibrated to explicitly account for data limitations, as well as rigorously evaluated based on multiple evaluation metrics. In the current deliverable AtlantECO-MAPS1, we present a compilation of biological target variables extrapolated to the global scale using state-of-the-art species distribution models and subsets of the ocean microbiome data delivered in AtlantECO-BASE1 (Vogt et al. 2023), as well as additional model outputs produced in related species modelling activities. These extrapolated maps may be of use for a wide stakeholder community, including partners in other work packages, i.e. project partners in WP3 (marine ecosystem health and services), WP5 (advances in systems ecology), WP6 (advances in model predictability), comparable with assessments carried out in WP7 (ecosystem change) and the work will contribute to WP8 (predictions of and for ecosystem services). Beyond AtlantECO, we believe that model outputs will be widely adopted by marine ecosystem modellers, remote sensing scientists, non-academic stakeholders such as policy makers, ecosystem managers and conservationists, as well as members of the education sector (teachers, museums).

Figure 1: Modelling pathway for the extrapolation of biological and other AtlantECO target variables to the global scale using species distribution modelling (Benedetti et al. 2021).

Here, we use established and newly developed methodologies to extrapolate the publicly available geo-referenced data on the marine microbiome and its functions and stressors/pollutants gathered in AtlantECO-BASE1 (Vogt et al., 2023) across taxonomic groups and sampling methods to generate global data products (for use in statistical mapping and extrapolation), with a particular emphasis on the Atlantic Ocean (All-Atlantic Microbiome Atlas; AtlantECO-MAPS1, D2.1; Vogt et al. 2023). We explore marine microbiome data from traditional (task 2.2.1), imaging (task 2.2.2), and genetic (task 2.2.3) sampling methods, as well as information on ecosystem functioning (carbon fluxes, task 2.2.4) and ecosystem pollutants (plastics, task 2.2.3). Observational data informing on the presence-absence, abundance, biomass and diversity of the marine microbiome are available for use in WP3 (marine ecosystem health and services), WP5 (advances in systems ecology), WP6 (advances in model predictability), comparable with assessments carried out in WP7 (ecosystem change) and will serve as inputs for the activities in WP8 (predictions of and for ecosystem services). We also serve a range of data products generated by AtlantECO partners in other projects that are of relevance for AtlantECO.

All geo-referenced data are provided as a collection of NetCDF files, and an initial collection of CMIP6 simulations for future projections is also made available (section 4.11; AtlantECO-CMIP6). A range of visualisation tools has been created to showcase our outputs, which will be of use in WP9 (communication, capacity building, and outreach; section 4.10). A second version of AtlantECO-BASE (D2.1) and of AtlantECO-MAPS1 (D2.4) are due towards the end of the project. All output products will be made available to partners belonging to our sister projects and the wider science community (WP10). The dissemination of the gridded and extrapolated data products as public data layers via AtlantECO’s GeoNode (<https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/>) is ongoing (SBE).

SUMMARY STATISTICS (list number of maps in folders per data type):

Data silo	Data subset & type	Variable name(s)	Number of mapped products	On GeoNode
Traditional	Biogeographic distribution (habitat suitability index, presence-absence) from Benedetti et al. (2021)	Min, max, median, mean and stdev of monthly species-level habitat suitability index (HSI) for 845 species	845 (341 phytoplankton species and 504 zooplankton species)	No
Traditional	Diversity from Benedetti et al. (2021)	Min, max, median, mean and stdev of monthly species richness for 14 plankton functional groups	28	Yes
Traditional	Biomass from Knecht et al. (2023)	Monthly biomass concentration (mgC m^{-3} $\mu\text{gC.m}^{-3}$)	2	No

Traditional	Biogeographic distribution (habitat suitability index) from Eriksson et al., in prep. (X. Li, MSc thesis, 2023)	Min, max, mean and stdev of monthly species-level habitat suitability index (HSI) for 843 planktonic species	843 phytoplankton species and 517 zooplankton species (326)	No
Traditional and Omics	Biogeographic distribution (habitat suitability index) and global diazotroph richness from Eriksson et al. (submitted)	Min, max, mean and stdev of monthly species-level habitat suitability index (HSI) for 14 planktonic diazotroph species	14 species (8 cyanobacterial and 6 non-cyanobacterial)	No
Omics	MAGs from Frémont et al., (2022)	Presence probability (0-1)	374 MAGs/SAGs	No
Omics	Bray-Curtis dissimilarity from Frémont et al., (2022)	Community dissimilarity index (0-1)	1	No
Omics	Biomes from Frémont et al., (2022)	Presence probability (0-1)	27 climato-genomic provinces	No
Imaging	UVP5-based biomass from Drago et al. (2022)	Mean annual biomass concentration (mgC.m^{-3})	20	No
Microplastics	Microplastics concentrations from Poli et al., in prep (G.Poli, MSc thesis, 2023)	Surface ocean microplastics concentration (in \#items.km^{-2} , log10 transformed)	1	No

4 AtlantECO-MAPS1: Data products

4.1 Modelling pathways, quality control and documentation (task 2.3; lead: ETHZ)

Where AtlantECO-specific model runs for AtlantECO-MAPS1 (D2.4) were made (e.g. Benedetti et al., 2021), species distribution models for the extrapolation of geo-referenced data in space and time were developed in accordance with community accepted standards for design and quality control procedures developed for the modelling of scarce and biased data (task 2.1), as detailed in Righetti et al., 2023 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.02.28.530497>), and some species distribution models have been documented in agreement with current community standards as documented in Zurell et al., (2020). Outputs of species distribution models and other analysis products that have been developed by external partners to the project, or initiated prior to the project start, are recorded as published.

4.2 Data access (ETHZ/SBE)

All data can already be accessed by the project team from a dedicated public transfer folder located at partner ETHZ. Global fields of all quantities mapped using statistical and machine learning tools are accessible at <https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/> in NetCDF format. MAPS is further hosted by and distributed through AtlantECO's GeoNode (<https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/>). Data submissions from previous publications are referenced with their original references and data DOIs, so that all data published in international data repositories can also be directly sourced from the respective original data providers.

A comprehensive list of all maps developed can be found in the **Appendix Table** to this document.

4.3 Mapped and extrapolated data products AtlantECO-MAPS1 (task 2.3; D2.4; lead: ETHZ/UNIROMA/SBE)

The submissions consist of geo-referenced fields of plankton distribution, abundance, biomass, community composition and diversity, as derived from AtlantECO-BASE1 (D2.1) and other data sources, extrapolated to the global scale using species distribution modelling (Guisan and Zimmermann, 2000).

A list of all data products can be found in **Table A 4.1**. Below please find a discussion of acquired data sets by scientific study.

4.3.1 Phytoplankton diversity from Righetti et al. (2019)

This data set contains phytoplankton species richness estimates from the binarized (presence—absence transformed) habitat suitability patterns of 536 – 538 phytoplankton species pertaining to the diatoms, dinoflagellates, coccolithophores, and a few minor groups, with the raw data based on data recorded in PHYTOBASE (Righetti et al. 2020).

Reference: Righetti, D., Vogt, M., Gruber, N., Psomas, A. and Zimmermann, N.E., 2019. Global pattern of phytoplankton diversity driven by temperature and environmental variability. *Science Advances*, 5(5), p.eaau6253, [doi:10.1126/sciadv.aau6253](https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aau6253).

Data content:

Variables: monthly species richness (ssp_rich)
Dimensions: longitude (360), latitude (180), z (time; 12)
Uncertainty estimate: yes, ensemble means
Data format: *.nc

Resolution:

Temporal grid: Monthly climatologies, 12 months
Time period: Observational period, contemporary ocean
Horizontal grid: degrees, 360x180
Depth: Surface-ocean only (mixed layer mean)

Methodology:

Models used: Generalized Additive Models (GAM), Generalized Linear Models (GLM), Random Forest (RF)

Model ensemble approach: yes

Background selection: Total and group-specific target group approach

Background ensemble: yes

Predictors: Sea surface temperature (T; °C), salinity (S), nitrate (NO_3^- ; μM), phosphate (PO_4^{3-} ; μM), and silicic acid [$\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$; μM] from World Ocean Atlas 2013 (1955–2012) fields. MLD (m) from de Boyer-Montegut et al. (2004). Photosynthetically active radiation (PAR; $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and chlorophyll (Chl; $\mu\text{g liter}^{-1}$) from the Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor (<https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov>). Sea surface wind stress (m s^{-1}) from the Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform (Atlas et al. 2011; <https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov>). Data on carbon dioxide partial pressure in the surface sea (pCO_2 ; μatm) from Landschützer et al. (2011). Derived predictors included photosynthetically available radiation over the MLD (MLPAR; $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) computed from T, MLD, and Chl, the excess concentration of NO_3^- , relative to the Redfield ratio of 16:1 (μM ; N-star), computed as $[\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$, and Si-star, the ratio of $[\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4]$ to $[\text{NO}_3^-]$. The temporal trends of T (dT/dt), NO_3^- ($d\text{NO}_3^-/dt$), PO_4^{3-} ($d\text{PO}_4^{3-}/dt$), $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ [$d\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4/dt$], and MLD ($d\text{MLD}/dt$) were considered. Logarithmic MLD, Chl, and nutrient levels to the base of 10 were used in addition to their original forms.

Predictor ensemble: yes, five ensemble members with different predictors ranked in univariate tests

Abstract of associated paper:

Despite their importance to ocean productivity, global patterns of marine phytoplankton diversity remain poorly characterized. Although temperature is considered a key driver of general marine biodiversity, its specific role in phytoplankton diversity has remained unclear. We determined monthly phytoplankton species richness by using niche modeling and >540,000 global phytoplankton observations to predict biogeographic patterns of 536 phytoplankton species. Consistent with metabolic theory, phytoplankton richness in the tropics is about three times that in higher latitudes, with temperature being the most important driver. However, below 19°C, richness is lower than expected, with ~8°–14°C waters (~35° to 60° latitude) showing the greatest divergence from theoretical predictions. Regions of reduced richness are characterized by maximal species turnover and environmental variability, suggesting that the latter reduces species richness directly, or through enhancing competitive exclusion. The nonmonotonic relationship between phytoplankton richness and temperature suggests unanticipated complexity in responses of marine biodiversity to ocean warming.

Key figure:

Figure 2: Monthly mean climatological surface ocean phytoplankton diversity, adapted from Righetti et al. (2019). Colors indicate the simulated number of species present during any given month of the year.

4.3.2 Phyto- and zooplankton species habitat suitability indices (HSI) and plankton functional group species richness from Benedetti et al. (2021) and Benedetti et al. (2023)

This set of maps is partitioned into two folders that correspond to two types of outputs: (i) global species-level monthly fields of habitat suitability indices (HSI, ranging between 0 and 1; also called ‘presence probability’) for phytoplankton and zooplankton, for the contemporary time period only (i.e., folder labelled ‘Species_habitat_suitability_Benedettietal.2021’); and (ii) functional group-level global monthly fields of species richness (estimated through the sum of species-level HSI) for the contemporary and future time periods (i.e., folder labelled ‘Groups_species_richness_Benedettietal.2021’).

In the first set of maps, each NetCDF file records the monthly: minimum (Min), maximum (Max), mean, median and the standard deviation (Stdev) of the species-specific HSI predictions issued from three species distribution models (see Benedetti et al., 2021 for details). These species distribution models were trained on species-level georeferenced occurrence (presence-only) data collectively gathered in the ‘ZooBase’ dataset (<https://zenodo.org/record/5101349>) which was part of AtlantECO’s D2.1. deliverables (REF TO D2.1?). Phytoplankton species (n = 341) were separated from zooplankton species (n = 504) on the basis that these two categories constitute two broadly-defined trophic levels (i.e., primary and secondary producers). For the sake of clarity, we do not list the names of all 845 species in this report.

In the second set of maps, each NetCDF file records the monthly: minimum (Min), maximum (Max), mean, median and the standard deviation (Stdev) of the species richness estimated for 14 different plankton functional groups (Amphipoda, Appendicularia, Calanoida, Chaetognatha, Coccolithophores, Diatoms, Dinoflagellates, Euphausiids, Foraminifera, Jellyfish, Oithonida, Poecilostomatoida, Pteropoda and Thaliacea). For each functional group, species richness was estimated as the sum of the HSI predicted for the species composing that functional group. The same three types of species distribution models were used as for the species-level HSI fields described above (see Benedetti et al., 2021 and Benedetti et al., 2023 for details). The main difference is that the species distribution models used to generate the data stored in the first folder relied on background data drawn from a “total target group approach”, whereas the models used for the data stored in the second folder were based on “group-specific target group approach” (Righetti et al., 2019, 2023; Benedetti et al., 2021, 2023). There are two NetCDF files per functional group here as we predicted the global species richness patterns for two different time periods: contemporary (2012-2031) and future (2081-2100). For projecting the species distribution models into the environmental conditions prevailing over the future time period, the future values of the environmental predictors used in the distribution models were extracted from

five different Earth System Models from the MAREMIP project: the Community Earth System Model version 1 (CESM1, POP-BEC), the Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory Earth System Model with Modular Ocean Model version 4 (GFDL-ESM2M; MOM-TOPAZ), the Institut Pierre Simon Laplace Climate Model version 5A-LR (IPSL-CM5A-LR; NEMO-PISCES), the Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques Climate Model version 5 (CNRM-CM5; NEMO-PISCES) and the Model for Interdisciplinary Research on Climate version 5 (MIROC5; MRI.COM-MEM).

Reference: Benedetti, F., Vogt, M., Elizondo, U.H., Righetti, D., Zimmermann, N.E. and Gruber, N., 2021. Major restructuring of marine plankton assemblages under global warming. *Nature Communications*, 12(1), p.5226, [doi:10.1038/s41467-021-25385-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-25385-x).

Benedetti, F., Gruber, N., and Vogt, M. 2023. Global gradients in species richness of marine plankton functional groups. *Journal of Plankton Research*, <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbad044>.

Data content:

Variables: Min/Max/Mean/Median and Stdev values of species-level HSI (n = 845 species) and functional group-level species richness estimates (n = 14 functional groups) derived from HSI

Uncertainty estimate: yes, ensemble means

Data format: *.nc

Resolution:

Temporal grid: Monthly, (12 months)

Time period: Observational period, contemporary (2012-2031) and future (2081-2100) ocean (5 Earth System Models forced by a RCP8.5 scenario) for the functional group-level species richness fields)

Horizontal grid: degrees, 360x180

Depth: Surface ocean

Methodology:

Models used: GLM, GAM Artificial Neural networks (ANN)

Model ensemble approach: yes

Background selection: Total target group approach for the species-level HSI fields (Benedetti et al., 2021) and group-specific target group approach for the groups' species richness fields (Benedetti et al., 2023)

Background ensemble: yes

Predictors: Monthly climatologies of the WOA13v2 (<https://www.nodc.noaa.gov/OC5/woa13/woa13data.html>) for sea surface temperature (SST, °C), sea surface salinity (SSS), nitrates (NO_3^-), phosphates (PO_4^{3-}) and silicic acid ($\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$) surface concentrations (μM), and dissolved oxygen concentration (dO_2 , ml l^{-1}). Monthly climatologies of Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR; $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and chlorophyll (Chl; mg m^{-3}) from the Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor (SeaWiFS; <https://oceancolor.gsfc.nasa.gov/>). Monthly climatologies of mixed-layer depth (MLD, m) based on the temperature criterion of de Boyer-Montegut et al. (2004) from the Argo floats data (<http://mixedlayer.ucsd.edu/>). Climatologies of surface wind stress (m s^{-1}) from the Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform (Atlas et al. 2011; <https://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/>). Climatologies of surface carbon dioxide partial pressure (pCO_2 ; atm) from the Surface Ocean CO_2 Atlas (SOCATv2; <https://www.socat.info/>; Bakker et al., 2014; Landschützer et al. 2014). Mean Eddy Kinetic Energy (EKE, $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$) from the daily satellite altimetry observations (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/#!/home>), following the method of Qiu & Chen (2011). Derived predictors included PAR over the MLD (MLPAR, $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; Brun et al. (2015), the annual range of SST (dSST), the excess of nitrate to phosphate (N^* , μM) relative to the Redfield ratio was computed as $[\text{NO}_3^-] - 16[\text{PO}_4^{3-}]$, and the excess of silicates to nitrates ($\text{Si}^* = [\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4] - [\text{NO}_3^-]$, μM). The logarithmic values were considered for skewed variables, i.e. $\log\text{NO}_3$, $\log\text{PO}_4$, $\log\text{SiOH}_4$, $\log\text{EKE}$, and $\log\text{Chl}$.

Predictor ensemble: yes, multiple predictor sets for each species

Climate model ensembles: yes, 5 ESMs, the Community Earth System Model version 1 (CESM1, POP-BEC), the Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory Earth System Model with Modular Ocean Model version 4 (GFDL-ESM2M; MOM-TOPAZ), the Institut Pierre Simon Laplace Climate Model version 5A-LR (IPSL-CM5A-LR; NEMO-PISCES), the Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques Climate Model version 5 (CNRM- CM5; NEMO-PISCES) and the Model for Interdisciplinary Research on Climate version 5 (MIROC5; MRI.COM-MEM).

Cautionary note: The species-level maps presented here were used to estimate global species richness patterns which were validated against previous findings whenever possible, peer-reviewed and published. However, please be aware that the individual species-level maps were not reviewed by independent experts and were mainly evaluated through common model skills metrics and visually examined by Fabio Benedetti. The species distribution models built for the study were designed to detect suitable environmental conditions based on the set of occurrences made available to the scientific community. As a result, some parts of the global ocean may show high habitat suitability values although the species modelled actually never occurs there due to a combination of complex biotic and abiotic factors that could not be integrated in the SDMs. We have greater confidence in the overall richness patterns than in the species maps due to various biases and assumptions made in the distribution modelling framework. Please use the species-level maps with caution and consider the limitations associated with outputs seeming from species distribution models.

Abstract of associated paper:

Marine phytoplankton and zooplankton form the basis of the ocean's food-web, yet the impacts of climate change on their biodiversity are poorly understood. Here, we use an ensemble of species distribution models for a total of 336 phytoplankton and 524 zooplankton species to determine their present and future habitat suitability patterns. For the end of this century, under a high emission scenario, we find an overall increase in plankton species richness driven by ocean warming, and a poleward shift of the species' distributions at a median speed of 35 km/decade. Phytoplankton species richness is projected to increase by more than 16% over most regions except for the Arctic Ocean. In contrast, zooplankton richness is projected to slightly decline in the tropics, but to increase strongly in temperate to subpolar latitudes. In these latitudes, nearly 40% of the phytoplankton and zooplankton assemblages are replaced by poleward shifting species. This implies that climate change threatens the contribution of plankton communities to plankton-mediated ecosystem services such as biological carbon sequestration.

Key figure:

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of the mean annual species richness (expressed in % of species modelled per group) for a) Diatoms (n = 163), b) Dinoflagellates (n = 157), c) Coccolithophores (n = 27), d) Calanoida (n = 221), e) Oithonida (n = 12), f) Poecilostomatoida (n = 41), g) Euphausiids (n = 51), h) Jellyfish (n = 69), i) Salps (n = 12), j) Pteropods (n = 19), k) Chaetognatha (n = 27), l) Amphipods (n = 20), m) Appendicularians (n = 6), and n) Foraminifera (n = 26). Blank areas correspond to those grid cells where richness projections were not possible for more than six months due to missing values in the monthly environmental climatologies the models were projected on.

4.3.3 Phyto- and zooplankton habitat suitability and species richness from MAPMAKER (Eriksson et al., in preparation; Xinhang Li, MSc thesis, 2023)

This dataset contains future projections of marine planktonic species ($n = 843$) based on the Habitat Suitability Index retrieved from an ensemble across Species Distribution Models accounting for several sources of uncertainty (algorithm complexity and climate models). In order to effectively store the data, we use the .zarr file storage system (<https://zarr.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>). Each species file can be opened and contains 5 dimensions (rcp, statistic, timesteps, latitude and longitude). The data covers the time period from 2012 until 2100 in monthly timesteps for three different RCPs (RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5). The statistics (mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum) are calculated across three different Earth System Models (CNRM-CM5, GFDL-ESM2M, IPSL-CM5A-LR) and three different algorithms (General Linear Model, General Additive Model and an Artificial Neural Network). The resolution of the data is 1° by 1° monthly resolution.

Reference: Eriksson et al., in preparation; Xinhang Li, MSc thesis, 2023, [doi:10.3929/ethz-b-000652200](https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000652200).

Data content:

Variables: Min/Max/Mean/Median and Stdev values of species-level HSI ($n = 843$ species; 326 phytoplankton species and 517 zooplankton species)

Uncertainty estimate: yes

Data format: *.nc

Resolution:

Temporal grid: Monthly climatological, 12 months

Time period: Observational period, contemporary and future ocean (RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5 from 4 ESMs)

Horizontal grid: degrees, 360×180

Depth: Surface ocean mixed layer mean only

Methodology:

Models used: GAM, GLM, RF

Model ensemble approach: yes

Background selection: Target group approach

Background ensemble: yes

Predictors: as Righetti et al. (2021) described above.

Predictor ensemble: No

Climate model ensemble: Three different Earth System Models have been used: the Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques Climate Model version 5 (CNRM-CM5), the Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory Earth System Model (GFDL-ESM2M), Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace Climate Model 5A-Long Range (IPSL-CM5A-LR).

Abstract: Marine plankton are at the base of the marine food webs. They perform essential ecological functions such as biological carbon sequestration and food provision to higher trophic levels. However, they are subject to anthropogenic climate change, and the impacts of different climate change scenarios on marine plankton biodiversity and habitat are poorly quantified. In this study, we use an ensemble of species distribution models to project habitat suitability index for a total of 843 marine plankton species (326 phytoplankton and 517 zooplankton) under three climate change scenarios (RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) from 2012-2100. The differences in plankton biodiversity among the three RCPs are substantial. In RCP2.6, compared to the baseline (2012-2031), the global mean relative increase in plankton species richness by the end of the 21st century (2081-2100) is only 1.6%. This relative change increases to 3.4% in RCP4.5 and further to 8.0% in RCP8.5. From RCP2.6 to RCP8.5, there is a remarkable expansion of species richness change hotspots. In RCP8.5, the species

richness change hotspots will cover three fourths of the global surface ocean from 60°N to 60°S by the end of the 21st century. The majority of plankton species (85%) will shift poleward in the future in response to ocean warming. Furthermore, there is a significant acceleration of poleward shift, from 3.76 km/dec in RCP2.6 to 19.95 km/dec in RCP8.5. The Arctic Ocean is the ocean basin that will experience the highest level of species turnover in plankton assemblages under all RCP scenarios, which indicates a high sensitivity to climate change in this region. Species turnover in the Arctic Ocean amounts to 0.45 in RCP8.5, which means that nearly half of the species in plankton assemblages will be replaced by the end of the 21st century. Phytoplankton and zooplankton are different in their biodiversity responses to ocean warming in the tropics: Phytoplankton species richness will increase under all RCP scenarios, by contrast, zooplankton species richness will slightly decrease in RCP8.5, and slightly increase in RCP4.5 and RCP2.6. Additionally, the dissimilarity of phytoplankton assemblage composition between baseline and future is driven by both turnover and nestedness, whereas the dissimilarity of zooplankton assemblage composition between baseline and future is primarily driven by species turnover. Overall, limiting global warming below 1.5°C can avoid the significant expansion of plankton richness change hotspots under RCP8.5 compared to RCP2.6, constrain the speed of poleward habitat shift below one fifth of that in RCP8.5, and keep the species turnover in the Arctic Ocean at about half of that in RCP8.5. Potential negative impacts on ocean carbon cycles and ecosystem services caused by marine plankton biodiversity change and habitat shift can be avoided if collaborative efforts are made to limit global warming below 1.5 °C.

Key figure:

Figure 4: Species richness (SR) and the uncertainties in species richness projections under baseline RCP2.6 scenario. (A1)-(C1) show the latitudinal profiles of SR for total (top), phyto- (middle) and zooplankton (bottom). (A2)-(C2) show the global patterns of SR for total, phyto- and zooplankton. (A3)-(C3) show the standard deviations in SR projections across the 9 ensemble members for total, phyto- and zooplankton. (A4)-(C4) show the latitudinal profiles of standard deviations for total, phyto- and zooplankton. SR and uncertainties are normalized to the total number of species (total plankton, $n = 843$; phytoplankton, $n = 326$; zooplankton $n = 517$). The blue shades in the latitudinal profiles indicate the standard deviation related to the average of a latitude band. From X. Li, MSc thesis, 2023.

4.3.4 Zooplankton calcifier biomass from Knecht et al. (2023)

This set of maps contains two NetCDF files that record the ensemble predictions of global monthly (12 time levels) biomass concentrations of calcifying Pteropoda (in mg C m⁻³) and Foraminifera (in µg C m⁻³). The monthly biomass concentration fields were obtained by training a suite of five distribution models tailored for predicting plankton biomass data obtained from traditional sampling techniques (see Knecht et al., 2023 for details). The observational data and the environmental layers used to train the biomass models were integrated over the epipelagic layer (0-200m) of the global ocean. Therefore, the predicted values are representative of the conditions prevailing in the epipelagic layer. The two NetCDF files thus record the: minimum (Min), maximum (Max), mean, median and the standard deviation (Stdev) of the monthly predictions issued from these five models.

Reference: Knecht, N.S., Benedetti, F., Hofmann Elizondo, U., Bednaršek, N., Chaabane, S., de Weerd, C., Peijnenburg, K.T., Schiebel, R. and Vogt, M., 2023. The impact of zooplankton calcifiers on the marine carbon cycle. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*, 37(6), [doi:10.1029/2022GB007685](https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GB007685).

Data content:

Variables: Min/Max/Mean/Median/Stdev of monthly total carbon concentrations of Pteropoda (mg C m⁻³) and Foraminifera (µg C m⁻³)

Uncertainties: yes

Data format: *.nc

Resolution:

Temporal grid: Monthly climatological, 12 months

Time period: Observational period, contemporary ocean

Horizontal grid: degrees, 360x180

Depth: Epipelagic layer (0-200m)

Methodology:

Models used: General Linear Models (GLM), General Additive Models (GAM), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM)

Model ensemble approach: yes

Background selection: not applicable (continuous data)

Background ensemble: not applicable (continuous data)

Predictors: The final set of predictors included temperature (from World Ocean Atlas 2018 (WOA); Locarini et al. 2018), and chlorophyll-a (SeaWiFS; NASA OB.DAAC 2018) for both plankton groups as well as mixed layer depth (MLD; from SODA3.4.2 (Carton et al. 2018)) for pteropods, and eddy kinetic energy (EKE; from Copernicus (Copernicus 2021)) for foraminifers. Additional predictors tested for inclusion were salinity, dissolved oxygen at 200 m depth, nitrate, and phosphate from WOA, the depth of the euphotic zone (z_{eu}), photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), particulate backscattering coefficient at 443 nm (BBP₄₄₃) and the diffuse attenuation coefficient for downwelling irradiation at 490 nm (Kd₄₉₀) from SeaWiFS, total alkalinity, dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC), the partial pressure of CO₂ (pCO₂) and the calcite and aragonite saturation state (Omega_{calcite} and Omega_{aragonite}) from Ocean-SODA-ETHZ (Gregor and Gruber 2021). Depth-resolved monthly climatological predictors from the WOA18 were averaged over the climatological mixed layer depth (MLD). The distribution of chlorophyll-a concentrations, nutrient variables, MLD, and eddy kinetic energy (EKE) were log-transformed.

Predictor ensemble: yes

Abstract of associated paper:

Shelled pteropods and planktic foraminifers are calcifying zooplankton that contribute to the biological carbon pump via the sinking of their calcareous shells. However, their importance for regional and global plankton biomass and carbon fluxes is not well understood. Here, we modeled global annual patterns of pteropod and foraminifer total carbon (TC) biomass and total inorganic carbon (TIC) export fluxes over the top 200 m using five species distribution models (SDMs). An extended version of the MARine Ecosystem DATA (MAREDAT; Buitenhuis et al. 2013) of zooplankton abundance observations was used to estimate the biomass of both plankton groups. We found hotspots of mean annual pteropod biomass in the high Northern latitudes and the global upwelling systems, and in the high latitudes of both hemispheres and the tropics for foraminifers. This largely agrees with previously observed distributions. For both groups, temperature is the strongest environmental correlate, followed by chlorophyll-a. We found mean annual standing stocks of 52 Tg TC (48 to 57 Tg TC) and 0.9 Tg TC (0.6 to 1.1 Tg TC) for pteropods and foraminifers, respectively. This translates to mean annual TIC fluxes of 14 Tg TIC yr⁻¹ (9 to 22 Tg TIC yr⁻¹) for pteropod shells and 11 Tg TIC yr⁻¹ (3 to 27 Tg TIC yr⁻¹) for foraminifer tests. These results are similar to previous estimates for foraminifers, but approximately a factor of ten lower for pteropods. Pteropods contribute 0.2%–3.2% and foraminifers 0.1%–3.8% to global surface carbonate fluxes. Including global coccolithophore fluxes, this leaves 40%–60% of the global carbonate fluxes unaccounted for. Our figures are likely lower-bound estimates due to sampling data characteristics and uncertainty associated with organism growth rates.

Key figure:

Figure 5: Global mean annual total carbon (TC) biomass concentration for pteropods (left, A) and foraminifers (right, B), averaged over all months and models. Values are shown as $\log_{10}(\text{TC} + 1)$, note also the different color scales for pteropods and foraminifers. Stippled regions in plots A - D indicate grid points where the environmental conditions were outside the training dataset for more than six months of the year as calculated with the Multivariate Environmental Similarity Surfaces (MESS) analysis. The lower panel plots C and D show the mean annual relative standard deviation of the model predictions for pteropods (left) and foraminifers (right), normalized with the mean prediction value at each grid point to facilitate comparison. Figure from Knecht et al. (2023).

4.3.5 Eukaryotic MAGs from Delmont et al. (2022), Bray-Curtis dissimilarity and climato-genomic provinces as reported in Frémont et al. (2022)

This data set contains the projected probabilities of presence of the 27 “climato-genomic provinces” described in Fremont et al. (2022) and originally defined in Richter et al (2022). They are projected using 10 year average ensemble climatologies (CMIP5) in the present day (2006-15) and in the future (2090-99, RCP8.5). Provinces encompass 6 size fractions of plankton that were sampled during the Tara Oceans expeditions (2009-2013): 0-0.2 μm enriched in viruses, 0.22-3 μm enriched in bacteria, 0.8-5 μm enriched in protists, 5-20 μm , 20-180 μm and 180-2000 μm enriched in small metazoans (mainly copepods). In addition, a global Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index (accounting for including the projected changes in the different size fraction) comparing present day and end of century projected provinces is included. This index is also projected on EEZ and main fisheries (from Watson, 2017). Finally, projected presence probabilities from 374 SMAGs from Delmont et al. (2022) are also available (present and future).

References:

1. Frémont, P., Gehlen, M., Vrac, M., Leconte, J., Delmont, T.O., Wincker, P., Iudicone, D. and Jaillon, O., 2022. Restructuring of plankton genomic biogeography in the surface ocean under climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 12(4), pp.393-401, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01314-8>.
2. Delmont, T., Gaia, M., Hinsinger, D., Frémont, P., Vanni, C., Fernandez-Guerra, A., Eren, A. M., Kourlaiev, A., d'Agata, L., Clayssen, Q., Villar, E., Labadie, K., Cruaud, C., Poulain, J., Da Silva, C., Wessner, M., Noel, B., Aury, J-M., Sunagawa, S., Acinas, S., Bork, P., Karsenti, E., Bowler, C., Sardet, C., Stemmann, L., de Vargas, C., Wincker, P., Lescot, M., Babin, M., Gorsky, G., Grimsley, N., Guidi, L., Hingamp, P., Jaillon, O., Kandels, S., Iudicone, D., Ogata, H., Pesant, S., Sullivan, M., Not, F., Karp-Boss, L., Boss, E., Cochrane, G., Follows, M., Poulton, N., Raes, J., Sieracki, M., Speich, S., de Vargas, C., Bowler, C., Karsenti, E., Pelletier, P., Wincker, P., Jaillon, O.. Functional repertoire convergence of distantly related eukaryotic plankton lineages abundant in the sunlit ocean, *Cell Genomics*, Volume 2, Issue 5, 2022, 100123, ISSN 2666-979X, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2022.100123>.

Data content:

Variables: Presence probabilities of 27 genomic provinces from Fremont et al. (2022) for present day and end of 10 year ensemble century climatologies + bray curtis dissimilarity index comparing present day (2006-15) and future (2090-99, RCP8.5). Presence probability of 374 SMAGs from Delmont et al. (2022) for present day (2006-15) and end of century (2090-99, RCP8.5) 10 year ensemble climatologies.

Uncertainty estimates: no

Data format: *.nc

Resolution:

Temporal grid: Monthly climatological, 12 months average

Time period: Observational period, contemporary ocean and projections in 2090-99 (RCP8.5)

Horizontal grid: degrees, 360x180

Depth: Epipelagic (0 - 200 m)

Methodology:

Models used: Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), Random Forest (RF), Neural Networks (NN), General Additive Models (GAM)

Model ensemble approach: yes, see below

Background selection: no

Background ensemble: no

Predictors: Physicochemical parameters included SST, salinity (Sal), dissolved silica (Si), dissolved nitrate (NO_3), dissolved phosphate (PO_4) from the gridded World Ocean Atlas 2013 (WOA13; Garcia et al. 2013), climatological dissolved iron (Fe) the biogeochemical model PISCES-v2 (Aumont et al. 2015) and a seasonality index of nitrate (SI NO_3). SI NO_3 is defined as the range of nitrate concentrations over the year in one grid cell divided by the maximum range encountered in WOA13 at the *Tara* Oceans sampling stations.

Predictor ensemble: no

Climate model ensemble, yes, ensemble of 6 Earth System Models 10 years climatologies (CMIP5, RCP8.5) for the 7 predictor variables, including CESM1-BGC (Gent et al., 2011), GFDL-ESM2G (Dunne et al., 2013), GFDL-ESM2M (Dunne et al., 2013), HadGEM2-ES (Collins et al., 2011), IPSL-CM5A-LR (Dufresne et al., 2013), IPSL-CM5A-MR (Dufresne et al., 2013), MPI-ESM-LR (Giorgetta et al., 2013), MPI-ESM-MR (Giorgetta et al., 2013), NorESM1-ME (Bentsen et al., 2013).

Abstract of associated paper:

1. The impact of climate change on diversity, functioning and biogeography of marine plankton remains a major unresolved issue. Here environmental niches are evidenced for plankton communities at the genomic scale for six size fractions from viruses to meso-zooplankton. The spatial extrapolation of these niches portrays ocean partitionings south of 60° N into *climato-genomic* provinces characterized by signature genomes. By 2090, under the RCP8.5 future climate scenario, provinces are reorganized over half of the ocean area considered, and almost all provinces are displaced poleward. Particularly, tropical provinces expand at the expense of temperate ones. Sea surface temperature is identified as the main driver of changes (50%), followed by phosphate (11%) and salinity (10%). Compositional shifts among key planktonic groups suggest impacts on the nitrogen and carbon cycles. Provinces are linked to estimates of carbon export fluxes which are projected to decrease, on average, by 4% in response to biogeographical restructuring.

2. Marine planktonic eukaryotes play critical roles in global biogeochemical cycles and climate. However, their poor representation in culture collections limits our understanding of the evolutionary history and genomic underpinnings of planktonic ecosystems. Here, we used 280 billion *Tara* Oceans metagenomic reads from polar, temperate, and tropical sunlit oceans to reconstruct and manually curate more than 700 abundant and widespread eukaryotic environmental genomes ranging from 10 Mbp to 1.3 Gbp. This genomic resource covers a wide range of poorly characterized eukaryotic lineages that complement long-standing contributions from culture collections while better representing plankton in the upper layer of the oceans. We performed the first, to our knowledge, comprehensive genome-wide functional classification of abundant unicellular eukaryotic plankton, revealing four major groups connecting distantly related lineages. Neither trophic modes of plankton nor its vertical evolutionary history could completely explain the functional repertoire convergence of major eukaryotic lineages that coexisted within oceanic currents for millions of years.

Key Figure:

Figure 6: Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index comparing present day (2006-15) and end of the century (2090-99) projections of climato-genomic provinces under RCP8.5 greenhouse gas emission scenario.

4.3.6 Nitrogen fixer biogeography and species richness from Eriksson et al. (submitted)

This data set contains monthly global marine diazotroph ensemble richness estimates from binarized (presence-absence transformed) habitat suitability patterns of 14 diazotroph species including cyanobacterial and non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs. We further provide the monthly ensemble biogeography of each individual species. Each netCDF file contains the ensemble average, standard deviation, maximum and minimum across all ensemble members.

Reference: Eriksson et al. (submitted)

Preprint: Eriksson, D., Righetti, D., Gruber, G., Benedetti, F., Paoli, L., Salazar, G., Sunagawa, S., Vogt, M., Nitrogen fixation rates increase with diazotroph richness in the global ocean, 2023. EcoEvoRxiv, <https://doi.org/10.32942/X2Z323>.

Data content:

Variables: ensemble_mean, ensemble_sd, ensemble_max, ensemble_min

Dimensions: longitude (360), latitude (180), z (time; 12)

Uncertainties: yes

Data format: *.nc

Resolution:

Temporal grid: Monthly climatological, 12 months

Time period: Observational period, contemporary ocean

Horizontal grid: degrees 360x180

Depth: Epipelagic (0 - 200 m)

Methodology:

Models used: GLM, GAM, RF

Model ensemble approach: yes

Background selection: Total, group-specific and cruise-specific target group approach

Background ensemble: yes

Predictors: exhaustive, see table below or consult corresponding paper

Predictor ensemble: yes

Candidate predictor	Variable nickname	Unit	Source
Sea surface temperatur	SST	degrees Celsius	World Ocean Atlas
Salinity	S	Practical salinity unit	World Ocean Atlas
Nitrate	N	μM	World Ocean Atlas
Phosphate	P	μM	World Ocean Atlas
Silicic acid	Si	μM	World Ocean Atlas
Mixed layer depth	MLD	meters	de Boyer Montégut 2004
Photosynthetically active radiation	PAR	$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$	Sea-Viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor
Chlorophyll	Chl	$\mu\text{g liter}^{-1}$	Sea-Viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor
Sea surface wind stress	SSW	m s^{-1}	Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform
Carbon dioxide partial pressure	pCO ₂	μatm	Landschützer, Gruber Bakker 2015
Photosynthetically active radiation over mixed layer depth	MLPAR	$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$	Brun et al., 2015
Excess concentration of nitrate relative to phosphate according to Redfield Ratio	Nstar	μM	$[\text{Nitrate}] - 16*[\text{Phosphate}]$
Ratio of silicic acid to nitrate	Sistar	μM	$[\text{Silicic acid}] / [\text{Nitrate}]$
Temporal trends of sea surface temperature	dT/dt	degrees Celsius	Difference on centered mean of each month with neighboring months
Temporal trends of nitrate	dN/dt	μM	Difference on centered mean of each month with neighboring months
Temporal trends of phosphate	dP/dt	μM	Difference on centered mean of each month with neighboring months
Temporal trends of mixed layer depth	dMLD/dt	μM	Difference on centered mean of each month with neighboring months
Logarithmic mixed layer depth	logMLD	μM	
Logarithmic chlorophyll	logChl	μM	
Logarithmic nitrate	logN	μM	
Logarithmic phosphate	logP	μM	
Logarithmic silicic acid	logSi	μM	
Sea surface height anomaly	SSH	meters	Aviso

Table 2: Parameters used to simulate diazotroph biogeography and diversity in Eriksson et al. (submitted).

Abstract of associated paper (preliminary):

Marine diazotrophs, a highly specialized group of marine prokaryotes, convert atmospheric nitrogen gas into bioavailable forms of nitrogen and are thus critical to maintain the fertility of the ocean. However, little is known about the link between global-scale diazotroph diversity and marine N₂ fixation rates. Here, we address this question by integrating DNA sequencing and microscopy-based observations for a total of 14 species into species distribution models to overcome data sparsity and uneven sampling efforts. Our study compiles diazotroph occurrences with more than 22'000 thousand observations and we identify distinct biogeographic

patterns for the major known taxa of diazotrophs, including colony forming, unicellular, symbiotic, and non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs. Non-cyanobacterial diazotrophs show higher habitat suitability in upwelling regions compared to their cyanobacterial relatives. A strong latitudinal gradient in diazotrophic richness emerges from these biogeographic patterns, with richness being highest in tropical and subtropical regions and declining towards the poles. Temperature and nutrient-related environmental parameters rank as the most important predictors of the biogeography explaining up to 36% of the variance for specific taxa. We find diazotroph richness to be positively correlated with nitrogen fixation rates, suggesting efficient resource partitioning rather than competitive exclusion as the dominant driver of the observed biodiversity patterns. Our work reveals that important biodiversity-ecosystem-function relationships associated with global biogeochemical cycling exist in marine plankton ecosystems, and suggests that global nitrogen fixation rates and diazotroph diversity are likely to increase in a warming ocean.

Key figure:

Figure 7: Global annual ensemble mean of diazotroph species richness based on presence-absence converted species distribution modelling outputs including a total of 14 species. White stipples indicate areas where the coefficient of variation between ensemble members was above the 70th percentile marking greater differences between model projections (from Eriksson et al., submitted).

4.3.7 4.3.9 Microplastics concentrations from Poli et al. (in prep.)

This NetCDF file contains global predictions of surface monthly microplastics concentrations (in #items.km⁻², log₁₀ transformed) modelled through five distribution models (GLM, GAM, ANN, RF, GBM). The models were trained on an observational dataset that aggregated measurements from multiple microplastic sampling campaigns compiled by van Sebille et al. (2015) and completed by Schmitz (2021). The original dataset of Schmitz (2021) synthesized no less than 13 159 microplastic concentrations observations spanning from 1979 to 2019. These microplastic concentrations measurements were collected through diverse sampling methods (~83% come from plankton nets) and covered plastics particles ranging from 32µm to 20cm. Giacomo Poli (MSc student, ETH Zürich) analysed this dataset and adapted the modelling pipeline of Knecht et al., (2023) (see section 4.3.4) to model global surface microplastics concentrations based on five types of statistical models mentioned above and an exhaustive suite of environmental and anthropogenic predictors (see table below).

Reference: Poli et al. (in prep); G. Poli, MSc thesis, 2023; doi:[10.5281/zenodo.10245292](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245292).

Data content:

Variables: Min/Max/Mean/NormSD of microplastics concentration (in #items.km⁻², log10 transformed)

Uncertainties: yes

Data format: *.nc

Resolution:

Temporal grid: Monthly, 12 months

Time period: Observational period, contemporary ocean

Horizontal grid: degrees, 360x180

Depth: Surface ocean mixed layer mean only

Methodology:

Models used: General Linear Model (GLM), General Additive Model (GAM), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Random Forest (RF), Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM)

Model ensemble approach: yes

Background selection: not applicable

Background ensemble: not applicable

Predictors: exhaustive, see table below or consult corresponding paper

Predictor ensemble: yes, 25 sets of 3, 4, 5 and 6 predictors

Table 1. Pool of all predictors divided into the 7 categories. The variable nickname is the name used to refer to the predictor.

Category	Candidate predictor	Variable nickname	Reference
Atmospheric	Eastward wind speed	wind_u10_era5	Hersbach et al. (2020)
	Northward wind speed	wind_v10_era5	Hersbach et al. (2020)
	Wind speed	windspeed_era5	Hersbach et al. (2020)
	Wind direction	wind_direction	Hersbach et al. (2020)
Bathymetry	Sea floor depth	bathymetry_min_etop1	Amante and Eakins (2009)
Biological activity	Chlorophyll	chlorophyll_seawifs	NASA OB.DAAC (2018a)
Human activity	Distance to closest coast	dist2coast	Amante and Eakins (2009)
	Distance to closest largest city	dist2cities	Amante and Eakins (2009), opendatasoft
	Distance to closest largest river	dist2rivers	Amante and Eakins (2009); Fekete et al. (2002)
	Fishing hours	fishing_hours	Kroodsma et al. (2018)
Location	Latitude	degree_north	-
	Longitude	degree_east	-
Physical and biogeochemical	Dissolved inorganic carbon	dic_surf_osethz	Gregor and Gruber (2021)
	Dissolved oxygen concentrations	oxygen	Garcia et al. (2019b)
	Mixed layer depth	mld_soda	Carton et al. (2018)
	Nitrate concentrations	nitrate	Garcia et al. (2019b)
	Phosphate concentrations	phosphate	Garcia et al. (2019b)
	Sea surface salinity	sss_cci_smos	Olmedo et al. (2017)
	Sea surface temperature	sst_oisstv2	Huang et al. (2020)
	Mixed layer photosynthetic active radiation	mipar1	NASA OB.DAAC (2018b)
	Photosynthetic active radiation	PAR	NASA OB.DAAC (2018b)
Transport	Currents direction	currents_direction	AVISO (2016)
	Currents divergence	divergence	AVISO (2016)
	Currents relative vorticity	relative_vorticity	AVISO (2016)
	Eastward geostrophic currents velocity	ugos	AVISO (2016)
	Eddy kinetic energy	EKE	EKE AVISO (2016); Qiu and Chen (2004)
	Geostrophic currents velocity	total_currents	AVISO (2016)
	Northward geostrophic currents velocity	vgos	AVISO (2016)
	Sea level anomaly	sla	AVISO (2016)
	Wind divergence	wind_divergence	Hersbach et al. (2020)

Table 3: Predictors used to train the microplastics model in Poli et al., in prep. and G. Poli, MSc thesis, 2023.

Abstract of associated paper (preliminary):

Marine microplastics pose a serious risk to the health of marine ecosystems, yet little is known about the concentration and spatial distribution of global surface ocean microplastics concentrations. Here, we use a data-driven, statistical approach to estimate global surface ocean microplastic concentrations and microplastic count per ocean basin by training an ensemble of statistical and machine learning models based on comprehensive observational datasets and a range of global environmental predictor variables. We found a clear pattern of microplastics accumulation in the subtropical gyres and in the Mediterranean Sea and lower microplastics concentrations in tropical and polar ocean regions. Oxygen and sea surface temperature were the strongest covariates of microplastics (34% and 33.2% of variance explained), indicative of strong latitudinal patterns and water age characteristics, followed by other physical and biogeochemical predictors (nitrate concentrations, dissolved inorganic carbon concentrations and mixed layer photosynthetically active radiation). We quantified a global mean surface microplastics concentration of $21\,250 \pm 1\,387$ items.km⁻², resulting in a global average microplastics inventory of 11.38 ± 0.76 trillion particles floating in the surface ocean. Our new inventory largely agrees with previously observed and modelled distributions using Lagrangian models but might represent a lower-bound estimate, given the lack of predictors associated with human plastic inputs in our approach. Our statistical approach has proven to be promising and might represent a computationally cheap complementary approach to the most used Lagrangian models, once predictors directly associated with human plastic inputs into the ocean are better constrained.

Key figure:

Figure 8: Global annual ensemble mean microplastic concentrations across all models and predictor sets. Values are shown as log₁₀ and expressed as items/km². Black points indicate the regions where the standard deviation between sets and models >0.75, indicating a higher set and/or model disagreement and therefore lower prediction confidence. From G. Poli, MSc thesis, 2023.

4.3.8 Zooplankton biomass from UVP5 observations as reported in Drago et al. (2022)

This set of maps contains 20 NetCDF files that record the predicted global mean annual biomass concentrations (in $\text{mgC}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) of diverse large zooplankton groups across variable ocean depth layers: Acantharea (0-500m), Annelida (0-200m), Appendicularia (0-500m), Chaetognatha (0-500m), Cnidaria (other than Hydrozoa and Siphonophorae; 0-200m), Collodaria (solitary forms; 0-500m), Collodaria (colonial forms; 0-200m), Copepoda (0-500m), Crustacea (other than Copepoda and Malacostraca; 0-500m), Ctenophora (0-200m), Doliolida (0-200m), Eumalacostraca (0-500m), Foraminifera (0-500m), Hydrozoa (other than Siphonophorae; 0-500m), Limacinidae (0-200m), Mollusca (other than Limacinidae; 0-200m), Ostracoda (0-500m), Phaeodaria (0-500m), Rhizaria (other than Foraminifera and Collodaria; 0-500m), and Siphonophorae (0-500m). These predictions of mean annual biomass concentrations were obtained by training Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) on observations of zooplankton organisms taken by multiple Underwater Vision Profiler version 5 (UVP5) throughout the globe and matched against annual climatological values of the environmental conditions. Because of the design of the underlying scientific study (Drago et al., 2022), the UVP5 data were partitioned between the epipelagic (0-200 m) and mesopelagic (200-500 m) layers of the ocean. As a result, the BRT were trained on zooplankton biomass concentrations estimated for these two layers separately. BRT predictions were thus also made and evaluated for these two layers separately. When mean annual carbon concentrations were skillfully predicted for both layers, they were recorded as such in the present NetCDF (i.e., values over 0-500m instead of 0-200m). Please see Drago et al. (2022) for further technical details.

Please note that these products have not been specifically created under the banner of AtlantECO. It is a product of opportunity that is publicly available and of scientific interest for the activities of AtlantECO and thus could be included in the current collection.

Reference: Drago, L., Panaïotis, T., Irisson, J.O., Babin, M., Biard, T., Carlotti, F., Coppola, L., Guidi, L., Hauss, H., Karp-Boss, L. and Lombard, F., 2022. Global distribution of zooplankton biomass estimated by in situ imaging and machine learning. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9, [doi: 10.3389/fmars.2022.894372](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.894372).

Data content:

Variables: Mean annual carbon biomass of Acantharea (0-500m), Annelida (0-200m), Appendicularia (0-500m), Chaetognatha (0-500m), Cnidaria (other than Hydrozoa and Siphonophorae; 0-200m), Collodaria (solitary forms; 0-500m), Collodaria (colonial forms; 0-200m), Copepoda (0-500m), Crustacea (other than Copepoda and Malacostraca; 0-500m), Ctenophora (0-200m), Doliolida (0-200m), Eumalacostraca (0-500m), Foraminifera (0-500m), Hydrozoa (other than Siphonophorae; 0-500m), Limacinidae (0-200m), Mollusca (other than Limacinidae; 0-200m), Ostracoda (0-500m), Phaeodaria (0-500m), Rhizaria (other than Foraminifera and Collodaria; 0-500m), and Siphonophorae (0-500m)

Uncertainties: yes (standard errors and standard deviations associated to the BRT predictions are recorded in the NetCDF files)

Data format: *.nc

Resolution:

Temporal grid: Monthly climatological, 12 months

Time period: Observational period, contemporary ocean

Horizontal grid: degrees, 360x180

Depth: Two depth layers;: 0-200m and 200-500m

Methodology:

Models used: Boosted Regression Trees (BRT)

Model ensemble approach: no

Background selection: not applicable

Background ensemble: not applicable

Predictors: In order to develop relationships between regional characteristics of the environment (Figures S2–4) and observed biomass, climatologies from the World Ocean Atlas (WOA) (Garcia et al., 2019) were used for temperature (in °C), salinity, oxygen (converted from $\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ to kPa for better physiological interpretation), and macronutrients (nitrate, phosphate and silicate in $\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$). We selected the data sets defined on a 1° horizontal grid, over the 0-500 m depth range, and with a monthly temporal resolution. Temporal coverage was from 2005 to 2017 for salinity and temperature and 1955 to 2017 for the other variables. We also used monthly averaged surface chlorophyll-a data (Chl *a* in mg m^{-3}) resolved to $1/24^\circ$ from 2005 to 2017 from the Copernicus database (OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_CHL_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_009_082) as well as bathymetry data from NOAA (Amante and Eakins, 2009) with a spatial resolution of 10 minutes; both were re-gridded to a 1° grid. Finally, distance to coast was computed by calculating the distance of all $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ cells to the closest cell associated to land using the raster package (Hijmans, 2021). To obtain annual climatologies, when relevant, each monthly variable was averaged over its time period of coverage.

Predictor ensemble: yes (implicit in method)

Abstract of associated paper:

Zooplankton plays a major role in ocean food webs and biogeochemical cycles, and provides major ecosystem services as a main driver of the biological carbon pump and in sustaining fish communities. Zooplankton is also sensitive to its environment and reacts to its changes. To better understand the importance of zooplankton, and to inform prognostic models that try to represent them, spatially-resolved biomass estimates of key plankton taxa are desirable. In this study we predict, for the first time, the global biomass distribution of 19 zooplankton taxa (1-50 mm Equivalent Spherical Diameter) using observations with the Underwater Vision Profiler 5, a quantitative *in situ* imaging instrument. After classification of 466,872 organisms from more than 3,549 profiles (0-500 m) obtained between 2008 and 2019 throughout the globe, we estimated their individual biovolumes and converted them to biomass using taxa-specific conversion factors. We then associated these biomass estimates with climatologies of environmental variables (temperature, salinity, oxygen, etc.), to build habitat models using boosted regression trees. The results reveal maximal zooplankton biomass values around 60°N and 55°S as well as minimal values around the oceanic gyres. An increased zooplankton biomass is also predicted for the equator. Global integrated biomass (0-500 m) was estimated at 0.403 PgC. It was largely dominated by Copepoda (35.7%, mostly in polar regions), followed by Eumalacostraca (26.6%) Rhizaria (16.4%, mostly in the intertropical convergence zone). The machine learning approach used here is sensitive to the size of the training set and generates reliable predictions for abundant groups such as Copepoda ($R^2 \approx 20\text{-}66\%$) but not for rare ones (Ctenophora, Cnidaria, $R^2 < 5\%$). Still, this study offers a first protocol to estimate global, spatially resolved zooplankton biomass and community composition from *in situ* imaging observations of individual organisms. The underlying dataset covers a period of 10 years while approaches that rely on net samples utilized datasets gathered since the 1960s. Increased use of digital imaging approaches should enable us to obtain zooplankton biomass distribution estimates at basin to global scales in shorter time frames in the future.

4.4 Data visualisation tools (web applications) for the visualisation of geo-referenced interpolated data (task 2.3; D2.4; lead: ETHZ/SU/UNIROMA1)

In order to process, interpret and visualise data, a range of web applications have been developed by the WP2 team. These tools include:

A PlotlyApp to serve biodiversity data from species distribution modelling to policy makers:

<https://mapmaker.ethz.ch/>

A user-friendly ShinyApp designed to support novice species distribution modellers. This application offers a guided step-by-step pipeline for calibrating and evaluating species distribution models. It is tailored for use with presence-only and presence-absence data and publicly available high-resolution predictor variables from Bio-ORACLE (<https://www.bio-oracle.org/>). Additionally, it allows users to upload custom predictors directly through the application interface (De Angelis et al., in preparation): <https://dandangelis.shinyapps.io/emocean/>. To overcome current memory limitations on shinyapps.io servers, the tool can be run locally using R software (<https://www.r-project.org/>), by running the following code lines:

```
install.packages("shiny")  
shiny::runGist("b4f2fddf2de6b20c49917a128bf41d62")
```

A ShinyApp for the visualisation of present day and end of century (RCP8.5 climate change scenario) niche areas of eukaryote plankton MAGs from Fremont et al. (2022) and Delmont et al. (2022):

<https://gigaplankton.shinyapps.io/TOENDB/>

A prototype for the automatized modelling of binary (presence-absence), quantitative (abundance and biomass) and relative (e.g., percentage of gene reads) data is under development for deployment within the framework of the EU project BlueCloud2026 (open science platform for the collaborative marine research): <https://blue-cloud.org/>, with a prototype for quantitative data designed and tested during the blue-cloud hackathon 2021 'Decode the Ocean' (<https://hackathon.blue-cloud.org/>) and tested and published in Knecht et al. (2023) as well as Poli et al., (in prep).

A predictor library for species distribution modelling of marine target variables that extends the currently available high-resolution Bio-ORACLE compilation (<https://www.bio-oracle.org/>; Assis et al., 2017) with climate grid resolution predictor variables (monthly, regular horizontal and WOA depth grid) is currently under construction in our EU sister project BlueCloud2026.

4.5 AtlantECO-CMIP6: Initial AtlantECO compilation of regridded CMIP6 model data for the extrapolation of biological data to different future climates (task 2.3; D2.4; lead: ETHZ/CEA/UBern)

An initial compilation of regridded future projections for selected CMIP6 models, variables and future scenarios can be found under: <https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/AtlantECO-CMIP6/>.

Models: GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1-2-HR,

Scenarios: historical, piControl, SSP126, SSP245

Time period: 1850-2014 (historical), 2015 - 2100 (future projections)

Variables: intpn2, intpp, mlotst, no3, o2, ph, phyc, so, spco2, thetao, tos, zooc, zos

Grid: regular degree grid; 360 (lon)x180 (lat) x 12 (months), with variable-specific depth resolution (surface versus full water column)

For further information about variables, grids, simulation set-ups, please consult the CMIP6 website (<https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-phase-6-cmip6/>) as well as Eyring et al. (2016) for simulation design and naming conventions.

We expect to enrich this compilation continuously with output from further CMIP6 models covering a wider range of predictor variables and models.

5 Conclusion

This first version of AtlantECO-MAPS (D2.4) provides a first collection of geo-referenced fields that contribute to an All-Atlantic Atlas of the marine ecosystems (D2.7) and aggregates extrapolated biological and pollutant maps across the taxonomic groups, data streams and multiple data silos included in this project. All data included in AtlantECO-MAPS will eventually be hosted on the AtlantECO GeoNode (<https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/>) and will thus be made available to the project partners and the general public in accordance with FAIR publishing principles. This collection also inspired and enabled the development of multiple data visualisation applications and triggered the development of automatised mapping pipelines, with prototypes thereof currently being developed within the sister project BlueCloud2026 and tested by further AtlantECO partners using further variable types. All modelling pipelines and data products will be made publicly available and many additional scientific projects exploring and discovering patterns in further data sets part of AtlantECO-BASE1 have been started, both within and beyond the project, with results to be expected to feed into AtlantECO-MAPS2.

6 References

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7 Appendix

7.1 Table A 4.1 AtlantECO-MAPS1: Extrapolated data sets gathered

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields; M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 09-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available, d: derived fields only.

Taxon/ Type	Description	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Phytoplankton species richness	Monthly Median/Min/Max/Stdev of habitat suitability indices (HSI) for 536-538 phytoplankton species; time period covered: climatological contemporary ocean	Files in https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/Phytoplankton_diversity_Righettietal.2019/	Monthly climatological mean species richness based on 536 to 538 phytoplankton species-level habitat suitability indices (HSI)	y	y	y	n	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch) Paper & Data: Righetti et al. 2019; doi:10.1126/sciadv.aau6253	Righetti et al. (2019); doi:10.1126/sciadv.aau6253	p
Phyto- and zooplankton species	Monthly Median/Min/Max/Mean/Stdev of habitat suitability indices (HSI) for 341 phytoplankton species and 504 zooplankton species; time period covered: 2012-2031	Files in https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/Species_habitat_suitability_Benedettietal.2021/	Habitat suitability indices (HSI) - contemporary conditions only	n	n	y	n	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch) Benedetti et al., 2021; doi:10.1038/s41467-021-25385-x	Benedetti et al. (2021) https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-021-25385-x	p
Phyto- and zooplankton taxonomic groups	Monthly Median/Min/Max/Stdev of species richness estimates derived from habitat suitability indices (HSI) for 3 phytoplankton groups and 11 zooplankton groups; time periods covered: contemporary (2012-2031) and future (2081-2100)	Files in https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/Groups_species_richness_Benedettietal.2021/ (28 files) One netCDF per plankton group and time period (contemporary and future), for 14 different groups: Amphipoda, Appendicularia, Calanoida, Chaetognatha, Coccolithophores, Diatoms, Dinoflagellates, Euphausiids, Foraminifera, Jellyfish, Oithonida, Poecilostomatoida, Pteropoda and Thaliacea	Monthly species richness estimates derived from habitat suitability indices (HSI) - Contemporary and future (RCP8.5) conditions	n	n	y	n	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch) Benedetti et al. (2021) doi:10.1038/s41467-021-25385-x Benedetti et al. (2023) https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbad044	Benedetti et al. (2021) https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-021-25385-x	p
Phyto- & Zooplankton (monthly) from the MAPMAKER project	Monthly Mean/Min/Max/Stdev of habitat suitability indices (HSI) and	Files in	Habitat suitability indices (HSI, aka presence probability) -	n	y	y	n	n	Contact: Dominic Eriksson (dominic.eriksson@usys.ethz.ch)		u

Taxon/ Type	Description	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
(Eriksson et al., in prep; X. Li, MSc thesis, 2023)	presence absence data for 3 phytoplankton groups and 11 zooplankton functional groups; derived biodiversity patterns for time span of 2012 - 2100	https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/Species_habitat_suitability_MAPMAKER_Erikssonetal_2022/	Contemporary and future ocean Dimensions: RCPs (rcp26, rcp45, rcp85), stat(mean, std, min, max), time, lat and lon. Data variables:859 (species_names)						X. Li, MSc thesis, 2023 MSc thesis: doi:10.3929/ethz-b-000652200		
Zooplankton calcifier biomass from Knecht et al. (2023)	Monthly median/mean/min/max /stdev pteropod and foraminifera biomass	Files in https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/Zooplankton_Calcifier_biomass_Knechtetal.2023/	Extrapolated biomass estimates for pteropods and foraminifera biomass, monthly climatology, 1x1degrees, WOA depth grid	y	y	y	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch) Paper: Knecht et al., (2023); https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GB007685 Model codes: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7888452 Data: https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.957258	Knecht et al., (2023) https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.957258	p
Eukaryotic Metagenomes Assembled Genomes (MAGs) from Delmont et al., (2022)	Modelled annual probability of presence for individual 366 MAGs and 8 SAGs for present (2006-15) and end of the century (2090-99) following RCP8.5 greenhouse gas emission scenario	Files in https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/Biogeographic_maps_Fremontetal.2022/MAGs_Delmontetal.2022/ AtlantECO-MAPS-v1_*_Delmontetal.2022_20221117.nc	presence probabilities MAGs (0-1), see readme	n	y	y	y	n	Contact person: Paul Frémont/Olivier Jaillon (pfermont@genoscope.cns.fr; ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr) Paper: Frémont et al., 2022; doi:10.1038/s41558-022-01314-8	Frémont et al. (2022) https://www.nature.com/articles/s41558-022-01314-8	u

Taxon/Type	Description	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
									Model code: https://github.com/institut-de-genomique/NCLIM-20102618B . Data: https://github.com/institut-de-genomique/NCLIM-20102618B . Raw data: Delmont et al., 2022; doi:10.1016/j.xgen.2022.100123		
Bray-Curtis Dissimilarity from Frémont et al., (2022)	Modelled annual Bray curtis dissimilarity index between present day and end of the century plankton biogeographies following RCP8.5 greenhouse gas emission scenario	Files in https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/Biogeographic_maps_Fremontetal.2022/Bray-curtis_dissimilarity_index_Fremontetal.2022/ AtlantECO-MAPS-v1_bray_curtis_dissimilarity_plankton_community_composition_*_Fremontetal.2022_20221117.nc	Bray-Curtis dissimilarity index (0-1), see readme	n	y	y	y	n	Contact person: Paul Frémont/Olivier Jaillon (pfermont@genoscope.cns.fr; ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr) Paper: Frémont et al., 2022; doi:10.1038/s41558-022-01314-8 Model codes : https://github.com/institut-de-genomique/NCLIM-20102618B . Data: https://github.com/institut-de-genomique/NCLIM-20102618B .	Frémont et al. (2022) https://www.nature.com/articles/s41558-022-01314-8	p

Taxon/ Type	Description	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Climato-genomic provinces from Frémont et al., (2022)	Annual modelled probabilities of presence of each "climato-genomic" provinces (Figure 3 and extended data Figure 4 of the article) for modelled present day (2006-15) and end of the century (2090-99) following RCP8.5 greenhouse gas emission scenario.	Files in https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/Biogeographic_maps_Fremontetal.2022/Climato-genomic_provinces_Fremontetal.2022/ AtlantECO-MAPS-v1_climato-genomic_province_*_Fremontetal.2022_2022117.nc	Size fractions and provinces probabilities of presence (0-1), see readme	n	y	y	y	n	Contact person: Paul Frémont/Olivier Jaillon (pfrémont@genoscope.cns.fr; ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr) Paper: Frémont et al., 2022; doi:10.1038/s41558-022-01314-8 Model codes : https://github.com/institut-de-genomique/NCLIM-20102618B . Data: https://github.com/institut-de-genomique/NCLIM-20102618B . Biomes: https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Biogeographies_genomic_provinces/19071620	Frémont et al. (2022) https://www.nature.com/articles/s41558-022-01314-8	p
Nitrogen fixer biogeography from Eriksson et al., (submitted)	Monthly Median/Min/Max/Stdev of habitat suitability indices (HSI) for 14 diazotroph species; time period covered: climatological contemporary ocean Monthly Median/Min/Max/Stdev of diazotroph	Files in https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/Diazotrophs_biogeographies_species_richness_Erikssonetal.submitted AtlantECO-MAPS-v1_microbiome+omics_monthly_surface_Diazotroph_species_richness_Erikssonetal._20230929.nc	Habitat suitability indices (HSI, aka presence probability) - contemporary ocean Species richness estimates based on presence-absence transformed HIS for the contemporary ocean						Contact: Dominic Eriksson (dominic.eriksson@usys.ethz.ch)	Eriksson et al. (submitted) Paper preprint: https://doi.org/10.32942/X2Z323 Data set: https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000635803	u

Taxon/ Type	Description	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
	richness across 14 diazotroph taxa; time period covered: climatological contemporary ocean	AtlantECO-MAPS-v1_microbiome+omics_monthly_surface_SPECIES_NAME_presence_Erikssonetal._20230929.nc									
Microplastics concentrations from Poli et al., (in prep); G. Poli, MSc thesis, 2023.	Monthly predicted ensemble mean, max, min and normalized stdv of microplastic concentrations using five statistical models (GLM, GAM, RF, GBM, ANN) and 25 different sets of predictors.	Files in https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/Microplastics_concentrations_GiacomoPoli_2023/	Monthly predicted ensemble mean, max, min and norm. stdv (log. 10 items km ²)	y	y	y	y	n	Contact person: Meike Vogt (meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch)	MSc thesis: Poli, G. MSc thesis, 2023. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10245291	u
Mean annual biomass of large zooplankton groups derived from UVP5 data (Drago et al., 2022)	Mean predictions of annual biomass derived from Boosted Regression Trees (BRT) trained on mean annual biomass concentrations of zooplankton groups derived from global UVP5 profiles, integrated over two depth ranges: 0-200m and 200-500m.	20 files in https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/Zooplankton_groups_biomass_UVP5_Drago_et_al._2022/ One netCDF file per large zooplankton group: Acantharea, Annelida, Appendicularia, Chaetognatha, Cnidaria (others), Collodaria, Collodaria (colonial), Copepoda, Crustacea (others), Ctenophora, Doliolida, Eumalacostraca, Foraminifera, Hydrozoa (others), Limacinidae, Mollusca (others), Ostracoda, Phaeodaria, Rhizaria (others), Siphonophorae.	Mean predicted biomass (mgC m ⁻³) + standard deviation + standard error of the predictions	n	y	y	n	n	Contact person: Laetitia Drago (laetitia.drago@imev-mer.fr) Paper: Drago et al., 2022; doi:10.3389/fmars.2022.894372 Raw data: Stemmann et al., (in prep.)	Drago et al., (2022) https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.894372	p